

**SPORTS HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT OF SPORT
DEVELOPMENT INDEX IN PADANG, WEST SUMATRA,
INDONESIA - EVALUATION STUDIES OF THE AVAILABILITY OF
SPORTS HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT**

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Abstract:

Sport Development Index is a way to measure the improvement of sport development in a region. This research measures sport development by using sports human resource management in Padang as the indicator. The purpose is to discover the quality of sports human resource management in Padang examined from *Sport Development Index* and to analyze the availability of sports human resource. This research is conducted in Padang, West Sumatra Province, by taking data from 3 institutions as the scope of studies including the Education Authority, National Sports Committee of Indonesia (KONI), and a local non-formal institution. The research method applies qualitative and quantitative approaches. The qualitative data is collected through observation, document analysis and interview, while the quantitative data is taken by using a norm method of *Sport Development Index*. The result shows that the number of sport development in Padang based on the index of sports human resource management is 0.00082. According to the *Sport Development Index*, this number is within the range of 0.000-0.499. It means that sports human resource management belongs to low category quantitatively and qualitatively, or in the other words the quantity is deficient and the quality is low. To conclude, the sport development in Padang belongs to low category, thus the regional government needs to pay more attention and improve the sport development in the city.

Keywords: sport development, human resource, Sport Development Index

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1. Introduction

The success of development, especially in human resource of a certain area, can be measured partially by observing how the fundamental problems on the society are resolved. The problems consist of poverty, unemployment, illiterateness, food security, and democracy uphold. Concerning this matter, the human development achievements are partially various in which the aspects have both success and fail outcomes.

The improvement in sport development is not measured from how much medals won from the national events like National Sport Week. According to National Sport System, the improvement needs to be associated with the human resource or the sport personnel participated in physical activities, the open space, the citizen participation, and the physical fitness of the citizens. All of the aspects are used to measure the sport development with SDI.

I took sports human resource since I wanted to discover the sport development in Padang from human resource point of view. Furthermore, the open space is widely dispersed in many areas of the city, the citizen participation is relatively high and the physical fitness is good already. From the reasons above, I write a research entitled *“Sports Human Resource Management based on the Improvement of Sport Development Index in Padang, West Sumatra”*.

2. Literature Review

Manullang (2002: 3) says that management has 3 definitions, which are a process, a collectivity of people doing management activities, and an art or a knowledge. Here, management as a process also has different meanings. George R. Terry in Soewarno Handyaningrat (1992: 20) mentions that as a process, management distinguishes planning, organizing, actuating the work administration, and controlling by using either the knowledge or art to complete the goals. In this context, management can be defined as a process comprised of those four elements.

In accordance with accumulation and globalization, the development of management knowledge creates various opinions for the functions. Untung Nugroho (2015:11) states about the main functions in management, such as planning, organizing, actuating/directing, and controlling.

This research employs a framework identifying the common functions of management, which are:

A. Planning

Charles A. Bucher and March L. Krotee (2002: 9) say that planning is a logical process to analyze the work together purposely by applying certain method and time allocated for the work. Besides, Untung Nugroho (2015: 11) defines that this element is a process to define the purpose of organization, to make strategy to achieve the goal, and to develop the work plan of organization. Terry in Harsuki (2016: 85) mentions that planning is the arrangement of the integrated and predetermined pattern of future activities.

B. Organizing

This aspect comes from 'to organize' which means conducting and arranging the organization for certain purpose. It also derives from 'organ', in which *Webstre'e New Collagiale Dictionary* notifies it as 'organon' from ancient Greek. Here, 'organ' means as an instrument or medium used for important activity or accomplishable purpose. In short, 'to organize' means arranging the separated parts to be a complete unity for doing activities or accomplishing the goal.

C. Actuating

According to The Liang Gie in Achmad P (2012: 78), actuating is the manager's activity in commanding, assigning, directing, guiding, and leading the employees or personnel to do the task in order to achieve the settled goal. This element involves with the activity of manager in starting and continuing the task settled within planning and organizing aspects to accomplish the goal. This element intends to actuate the members of organization to feel motivated.

D. Controlling

This aspect can be defined as a process to apply, evaluate, and correct the finished task to make sure that it is in line with the plan (Manullang, 2002: 173). Nugroho Untung (2015: 27) explains this aspect as a controlling activity to keep the organization's performance on the right track and to ensure that the goal can be achieved.

Sport Development Index is a combining index which reflects the successfulness of sport development measured from 4 basic dimensions, which are the open space, human resource or sport personnel participated in physical activities, the citizen participation to do regular physical activities, and the physical fitness level of the citizens.

Sport pillar in UU No. 3 Year 2005 about sport system mentions that it does not only involve with the achievement but also education and recreation. Regarding this

matter, the successfulness is not measured merely by the medals, especially if they are worthless or won from doing improper way. Therefore, *Sport Development Index* (SDI) emerges as an idea to represent the sport development success and to measure sport development improvement in a region.

3. Research Methodology

This research was conducted from December 2016 to January 2017. It belongs to descriptive quantitative research since the substance and the focus concern with sports development studies. The result is presented through numbers. The data collection methods are consisted of observation, interview, and documentation.

I focused on the teachers and lecturers of physical education, coaches, instructors, and the referees to observe the availability of sports human resource. I counted the index after I got the numbers. First, I found the actual value by dividing the total amount of sports human resource with the citizens above 7 years old. The maximum value, which is already settled by SDI, is 2, 08 while the minimum value is 0, 00. Then, I counted the results with the formula below:

$$HR\ Index = \frac{Actual\ Value - Minimum\ Value}{Maximum\ Value - Minimum\ Value}$$

After all the indexes are counted and the whole index value is obtained, the last step is to determine the category or norm of the value index for justification. The employed SDI norm is:

Table 1: SDI Norm (Kristiyanto, 2012: 49)

Number of Index
0.800-1.000
0.500-0.799
0.000-0.499

4. Results of Research and Discussion

Table 2: Sports Human Resource at the Education Authority in Padang

Professions		Gender		Certification	
		Male	Female	Certificated	Non-certificated
PE Teacher	Elementary School	217	222	185	254
	Junior High School	64	37	85	16
	High School	84	31	77	38
	Lecturer	60	7	45	22
Total		425	297	392	330

Table 3: Sports Human Resource at KONI in Padang

Professions		Gender		Certification	
		Male	Female	Certificated	Non-certificated
PE Teacher	Elementary School				
	Junior High School				
	High School				
Coaches		168	72	112	128
Instructors		33	21	3	51
Referees		278	67	345	0
Total		479	160	460	179

Table 4: Sports Human Resource at a Non Formal Institution in Padang

Professions		Gender		Certification	
		Male	Female	Certificated	Non-certificated
PE Teacher	Elementary School				
	Junior High School				
	High School				
Coaches		8	0	0	8
Instructors		33	14	0	47
Referees		0	0	0	0
Total		41	14		55

The observation results for the sports human resource are gathered from the Education Authority, the National Sports Committee of Indonesia (KONI), and a non-formal institution. They show that the total of the sports human resource in the city is 1416 people and the total of citizens above 7 years old is 845. 915. Thus, the actual value is taken by using the formula of HR index, which is $1416 / 845.915 = 0.0017$.

In short, the index result above concludes that the index value of the sports human resource in Padang can be described as:

Table 5: The Index Value

No.	Institutions	Index Value	Criteria
1	Education Authority	0.00041	Low
2	KONI	0.00033	Low
3	Non-formal Institution	0.00003	Low
Total of Index Value		0.00082	Low

5. Conclusion

Based on the data analysis result, it can be concluded that the value of sport development result measured by *Sport Development Index* is 0, 00082. The index value is categorized as low. The data also show specific results, such as:

1. The index of sports human resource in Padang measured by *Sport Development Index* is 0.00082. This number is within the range of 0.000-0.499, means that it belongs to low category. In this context, sports human resource is classified as deficient quantitatively and low qualitatively.
2. The number for the whole availability of sports human resource in Padang is 945 for male and 471 for female, thus the total amount is 1416 people.

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